

SOCIAL NETWORKING FOR MANAGEMENT OF UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated social networking sites for effective management of universities in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Three research questions and two null research hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 6,245 respondents. The sample was 376 respondents derived from the population using Taro Yamene formula. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select the sample. The instrument used for data collection was “Social Networking Sites University Management Questionnaire (SNSUMQ). A face and content validity was done by three experts in the Department of Educational Management and Measurement & Evaluation of the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was ascertained using the test-retest method. The data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and z-test. The results showed that: the social networking sites in university management are Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp. The networking sites are mainly used for communication, meeting schedule notices, and enhancement of advertisement. Social networks are used by university management to a high extent in the management of Universities in River State. The three null hypotheses that were formulated and tested were rejected. It implied that gender played a major role in how choices are made by male and female administrators on the use of social network sites in the management of the university in Rivers State. The study, therefore, recommended University should make it a policy to incorporate other social network sites such as LinkedIn, Myspace, QQ, QZone, YouTube, and Zoom. Besides, the gender gap should be bridged by organising orientation, conferences, workshops, or seminars on the use of social network sites by the administrative staff of universities in Rivers State.

Key Words: Social Networking, University, Management.

I. Introduction

Education is widely accepted as a major instrument for promoting socio-economic, political and cultural development in Nigeria. The guiding principle of education in Nigeria is the inculcation into every citizen knowledge, skills, attitudes and values to enable them to derive maximum benefits from society by leading a fulfilled life, and contributing to the development and welfare of their community. Odekunle, (2001) opined that universities educate future leaders and develop the high-level technical capacities that underpin economic growth and development. Besides, Ibukun, (1997) posited that the main purpose and relevance of university education in Nigeria is the provision of much-needed manpower to accelerate the socio-economic development of the nation. The attainment of high-level manpower that promotes social change and economic development can only be feasible through the effective management of universities.

Managing universities is not a one-man’s task. Waddell, Jones and George (2011) stated that management is planning, organizing, leading and controlling human and material resources to achieve organizational goals efficiently and effectively. Kim and Christen (2013) defined management as the pursuit of organizational goals by integrating the work human effort through planning, organizing, leading and controlling the organizations’ resources. According to

Mgbekem (2004), several faculties, departments and operational centres exist as subsystems in university management. These subsystems have their patterns when it comes to putting forward views, positions and decisions on pertinent issues. This was the primary reason why Akindutire (2004) posited that managing universities is done on the committee system and no one individual takes and implements decisions alone. Thus the internal managing of Nigerian universities is teamwork of staff and students who are in these institutions on a day-to-day basis and are interactive with each other during different activities and functions approved by the statute establishing their universities.

Sustainability and continuous improvement are the essential benchmarks for organizational decision-making. This can be integrated into all functional areas of the organization and applied to traditional decision-making tools and used as an assessment tool for decision-making. So many organizations have applied integrated management to improve functionality and efficiency in various departments to improve outcomes in management. Universities are not left out in improving management efficiency. Various aspect of integration has been made in time pass into the management of universities like the use of the internet, information technology, websites and e-registration and examinations. The world is now integrating the use of social media or social networking into all spheres in buying, selling, advertising and information sharing. The education sector is not an exception.

The term social media or social networking refers to the use of web-based and mobile technologies to turn communication into an interactive dialogue. Social media takes on many different forms including magazines, Internet forums, weblogs, social blogs, microblogging, wikis, podcasts, photographs or pictures, video, rating and social bookmarking. With the world amid a social media revolution, it is more than obvious that social media like Facebook, Twitter, Orkut, Myspace, Skype and LinkedIn etc., are used extensively for communication (Paul, 2019). Therefore, social networking sites are described as web-based services that allow individuals to, construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection and view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system. The idea of social networking has existed for several decades as a way for people to communicate in society and build relationships with others using networking sites. The advancement in technology has made the use of network sites more frequent and thus becoming a norm in the educational system as a means of communication.

The Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) estimated that there are over 200 different network sites that are used for social networking (Gross, 2010). They noted that most people who are members of these sites, such as Facebook (over 400 million users) and Myspace (over 100million users) participate in them daily. Each person who becomes a member of a Social Network Site has the opportunity to create his or her webpage or profile which is supposed to be seen as a reflection of that person's personality. By using a personal profile, one can build an entire social network based on your personal preferences (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). The idea behind most of this phenomenon, as with many websites, is to help people feel socially connected and become part of a community (Coyle & Vaughn, 2008). Participants may connect with other people they know through school, work, or an organization or they may meet strangers from all over the world on which new relationships are built. Being a medium for social interaction, it is presumed that using social networking may enhance the flow of information for the effective management of universities.

The use of social networking has been so widespread that they have caught the attention of various sectors worldwide. Networking is an activity or process that has always been with us. Simply, it is the act of reaching out and connecting to others. In this way, we have always been

networking by sharing information between individuals that provides enough value to justify and maintain the relationship. Some of these behaviours according to Jukić and Merlak (2017), are purely utilitarian (meaning there is some gain to be had), whereas other behaviours are more focused on the socializing aspects of the relationship itself. Although networking actions have always been a part of human behaviour, the term was first used years ago by sociologists as they described the “web” of relationships in societies. This extended the metaphor of the “fabric” of society that many people were comfortable with within the preindustrial days. It illustrated the understanding that people are fundamentally connected and interdependent as part of their identity. This behaviour might come more easily to some than others, but it can be seen and learned by virtually anyone. In an educational setting, these activities include sharing or searching for information, knowledge, and expertise, as well as the more purposeful behaviour of collaboration, which generally assumes that there is a mutual goal involved. This collaboration according to Ladika, (2010), includes co-authoring, working together, and mutual support.

Social networking and collaboration are two related, but distinct, concepts that exist in contemporary times in human relations. It is often understood that social networking contributes to collaboration but is a more fundamental set of behaviours. Networking by itself does not necessarily require this but does provide a social context for more productive collaboration. Networks can be very dynamic or stable. Individuals are continually joining or leaving networks based on changing interests. On the other hand, Nwabueze & Obaro, (2011) noted that many networks are represented in communities that outlast the organizational structures. They are developed within, and between, the typical organizational structures that are meant to support the normal flow of work. Departments and project teams are formal groupings of people to get the work done, whereas “communities of practice” can be an informal, voluntary network that coalesces around topics of interest. Many social networking behaviours are common to these two different approaches, formal and informal. Social networks are more accessible by social networking sites and applications in form of a desktop or mobile applications.

Social networking sites are now being investigated by numerous social science researchers and an increasing number of academic commentators are becoming more and more interested in studying Facebook, Twitter, and other social networking services, because of their probable impact on society (Raacke & Bond-Raacke, 2008; Asif & Khan, 2012). Most sites help people connect with others through shared personal interests, political and economic views, or simply recreational activities. Some sites accommodate distinct viewers, while others attract people based on similarities, such as common languages or shared racial, sexual, religious or nationality-based identities. Nonetheless, social networking sites have only one common goal. It is to encourage new ways to communicate and share information in different ways.

Social networking sites serve different purposes and their uses differ accordingly. For instance, *WhatsApp* is a free, multiplatform messaging app that enhances video and voice calls with just a Wi-Fi connection. As well as being free, it's more versatile than SMS. You can send volumes of photos, videos, and audio files, make video calls and voice calls, leave someone on a video message, and more. *Twitter* is another 'microblogging' social networking site that allows allowing people to share their thoughts with a big audience with short posts called tweets. Tweets can be up to 140 characters long and can include links to relevant websites and resources. Twitter users follow other users. If you follow someone you can see their tweets in your Twitter 'timeline'. Another social network site is *Facebook*. It is a website

that allows users, who sign-up for free profiles, to connect with friends, work colleagues or people they don't know, online. It allows users to share pictures, music, videos, and articles, as well as their thoughts and opinions with many people they like. *Facebook's mission* is to give people the power to build community and bring the world closer together. People use Facebook to stay connected with friends and family, to discover what's going on in the world, and to share and express what matters to them.

Skype, another social networking site with a VoIP service that enables people to make and receive free voice and video calls over the internet using a computer, web browser, or mobile phone. ... Along with chatting with people in your in-app contacts, you can also use it to make international calls cheaper. *LinkedIn* is another online platform that connects the world's professionals. A complete LinkedIn profile will summarize your professional experience to your connections, current and future employers, and recruiters. Through your profile, you can showcase your professional life, milestones, skills and interests. Another popular social networking site is MySpace. Originally founded as a venue for aspiring musicians and bands to share music and concert dates, MySpace has grown into a complex site where users can create profiles, including photographs, blogs, and music or movie preferences. Myspace has had a significant influence on technology, pop culture and music. It was the first social network to reach a global audience. Another social network site is YouTube. It provides a simple way for people to store videos online and share them with others. YouTube is a video sharing service that allows users to watch videos posted by other users and upload videos of their own. Xanga is a social networking Web site that hosts personal profiles, blog posts and photo sharing. The site is part of the Web 2.0 movement, where users of Xanga have a great deal of control over the content that gets created. On top of being able to post blogs on nearly any topic of their choosing, members have a good deal of independence over what their profiles can look like. Xanga may also be helpful to bloggers concerned about privacy and safety. The site offers several security features that let users control who can view their posts and what type of content is appropriate.

The use of these social networking sites as well as email, instant messaging, blogging, and online journals have completely changed the way that people interact and gather information in the university system. Raacke & Bond-Raacke (2008) noted that in contemporary times, people have become accustomed to using social network sites much more than older generations have in recent years. Organizations and individuals alike have subscribed to the use of social networking for their day to day activities. These activities include dissemination of information, group meetings, calling, messaging and making various transactions. The use of social networking in the academic sphere may not be left out. Perhaps the use of social networking in educational institutions may also have plausible implications for management. This is because the internet has become the tool used for everyday work in our lives. In recent studies, corporate business organizations have shown to be the greatest consumers of the Internet, particularly for social interactions (Lin & Subrahmanyam, 2007). However, the extent to which education institutions use social networking sites in managing daily activities is yet to be verified which this study tends to fill.

II. Statement of the problem

In most organizations, the effective management of human and non-human resources brings progress, satisfaction and plausible results. In the case of universities, staff and students are expected to benefit from the university authority. However, in course of managing the university policies and programmes and activities, there are delays in processing information,

delays in responding to applications, registration processes, clearance, and other university's programmes and activities. These duties are carried out by universities in the western world through the adoption of modern technologies called social networking. World over, social networking has been adopted as an instrument par excellence for university management, yet the universities in Nigeria, especially Rivers State are delaying in executing her programmes and activities. Premised on the foregoing, there is a need to investigate the usage of social networking sites for the effective management of universities in Rivers State to provide plausible empirical data. The problem of the study is therefore put in question form: What are the social networking sites for managing universities in Rivers State?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate the social networking sites are for managing universities in Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study include to:

1. *Determine the available social networking sites for managing universities in Rivers State.*
2. *Determine the areas social networking sites are used for managing universities in Rivers State.*
3. *Examine the extent of social networking sites is used in managing universities in Rivers State.*

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- 1 *What are the available social network sites for the management of universities in Rivers State?*
- 2 *What are the areas social network sites are used in the management of universities in Rivers State?*
- 3 *To what extent are social network sites used for managing universities in Rivers State?*

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated and testable at a 0.05 level of significance.

1. *There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female administrative staff on the social network sites used in the management of universities in Rivers State.*
2. *There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female administrative staff on the areas social network sites are used management of universities in Rivers State.*
3. *There is no significant difference in opinion of male and female administrative staff on the extent social network sites are used in the management of universities in Rivers State.*

III. Methodology

The study used a descriptive research design. The population of the study was 6,245 respondents. This comprised all the administrative staff in three universities in Rivers State, which are: University of Port Harcourt (4,306), Rivers State University (1,384), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (555). The sample size for the study was 376 determined using Taro Tamane formulas. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed in selecting the sample size. In the first stage, a stratified random sampling technique was used to select 260 respondents from the University of Port Harcourt, 83 staff from Rivers State University and 33 respondents from the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. In the second stage, purposive sampling was used to select the Administrative staff in the universities. The instrument used for data collection was "Social Networking Sites University Management Questionnaire (SNSUMQ). The instrument was validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Management

and Measurement and Evaluation in the Faculty of Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was ascertained using the test-retest method. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation scores while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The responses of the instrument were structured with a 4-point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1, and Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (LE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) respectively.

Results

The results from the research questions and hypotheses are presented in tables as follows:

Results of Research questions

Research Question One

What are the social network sites used in university management in Rivers state?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of administrative staff on the network sites used in managing universities in Rivers state

(N=372)

S/N	Question Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Rank	Decision
1.	University management uses Skype	2.07	.97	6 th	Disagree
2.	University management uses Facebook	3.91	.88	1 st	Agree
3.	University management uses Twitter	2.98	.82	3 rd	Agree
4.	University management uses YouTube	2.43	.79	4 th	Disagree
5.	University management uses WhatsApp	3.84	.67	2 nd	Agree
6.	University management uses LinkedIn	2.11	.79	5 th	Disagree
Cluster Mean		2.88	0.83		Agree

Table 1 showed that item 1 has a mean and standard deviation score of 2.07 and .97 respectively. This implies that the respondent disagrees that Skype as a social networking site is not used in university management in Rivers State. Item 2 has a mean and standard deviation score of 3.91 and .88 respectively. This implies that the respondent agrees that Facebook as a social networking site is used in university management in Rivers State. Item 3 has a mean and standard deviation score of 2.98 and .82 respectively. This implies that the respondents agree that Twitter as a social networking site is used in university management in Rivers State. Item 4 has a mean and standard deviation score of 2.43 and .79 respectively. This implies that the respondents disagree that YouTube as a social networking site is not used in university management in Rivers State. Item 5 has a mean and standard deviation score of 3.84 and .67 respectively. This implies that the respondents agree that WhatsApp as a social networking site is used in university management in Rivers State. Item 6 has a mean and standard deviation score of 2.11 and .79 respectively. This implies that the respondents disagree that LinkedIn as a social networking site is not used in university management in Rivers State. The cluster mean and standard deviation were 2.88 and 0.83 respectively. This indicates social networkings sites are used by universities management in Rivers State are Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp.

Research Question two

S/N	Question Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Decision
https://sgi-journals.com/				

7.	University management uses Social networks (SN) to discharge academic and administrative duties	2.53	0.92	Agree
8.	Social networks (SN) are used for notification of events	2.69	0.88	Agree
9.	SNS are used for administrative purposes	3.13	0.65	Agree
10.	Social Network (SN) is used to invite staff to meetings	3.18	0.69	Agree
11.	University management uses (SN) for teaching and learning	2.58	0.70	Agree
12.	University management uses (SN) for communication in the school's system	3.24	0.65	Agree
13.	University management uses (SN) for recruitments	2.56	0.73	Agree
14.	University management uses (SN) for online degree programmes and lectures	2.21	0.77	Agree
15.	University management uses (SN) for recording meeting proceedings	2.50	0.86	Agree
16.	Universities use social network sites to resolve conflicts	3.02	0.80	Agree
17.	SN is used for the publication of universities events	3.27	0.62	Agree
18.	SN is used to make public relations work easier	3.23	0.62	Agree
19.	SN is used to access information, materials and documents sharing easier	3.37	0.54	Agree
20.	SN is used to make media documents sharable in a short time	3.27	0.67	Agree
21.	SN is used for gratification and to create a relationship between the staff of universities.	3.34	0.53	Agree
	Cluster Mean	2.81	0.71	Agree

What is the areas social networking sites used in managing universities in Rivers state?
 Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of administrators on areas social networking sites are used in university management in Rivers State.

Table 2 showed that items 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 15 - 21 had high means scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. Item 7 has a mean score of 2.53 and a standard deviation of 0.92. This means that respondents agreed that Social Networking (SN) to discharge academic and administrative duties in universities management in Rivers State. Item 8 had a mean score of 2.69 and a standard deviation of 0.88. This means that respondents agreed that Social Networking Sites (SNS) are used for notification of events in universities management in Rivers State. Item 9 had a mean score of 3.13 and a standard deviation of 0.65. This means that respondents agreed that Social Networking (SN) is used for administrative purposes by universities management in Rivers State. Item 10 had a mean score of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.69. This means that respondents agreed that universities management uses (SN) for advertisement. Item 11 had a mean score of 2.58 and a standard deviation of 0.65. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) for teaching and learning in the school system. Item 12 had a mean score of 3.24 and a standard deviation of 0.65. This

means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) as a communication tool in their management systems. Item 15 had a mean score of 2.50 and a standard deviation of 0.86. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) for meetings schedules. Item 16 had a mean score of 3.02 and a standard deviation of 0.80. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SNS) to solve administrative challenges. Item 17 had a mean score of 3.27 and a standard deviation of 0.62. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) for the publication of universities events. Item 18 had a mean score of 3.23 and a standard deviation of 0.62. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) to make public relations work easier. Item 19 had a mean score of 3.37 and a standard deviation of 0.54. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) to access information, materials and documents sharing more easily. Item 20 had a mean score of 3.27 and a standard deviation of 0.67. This means that respondents agreed that university management uses (SN) to make media documents shareable in a short time. Item 21 had a mean score of 3.34 and a standard deviation of 0.53. This means that respondents agree that university management uses social networks sites for gratification and create a relationship between the staff of universities. The cluster means score and standard deviation were 2.81 and 0.71 respectively. This shows that areas of applicability of social network sites are: to discharge academic and administrative duties, administrative purposes, for notification of events, invite staff for meetings teaching and learning, communication, for recruitments, for online degree programmes and lectures, for recording meeting proceedings, to resolve conflicts, and for publication of universities events.

Research Question Three

What is the extent to which social networks Sites are used in the management of universities in Rivers state?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of administrators on the extent social networks Sites are used in managing universities in Rivers state. (N=625).

S/No.	Question Items	Mean (\bar{X})	SD	Decision
22.	SN is used for all notices for meetings and other functional purposes.	2.70	1.11	HE
23.	SN is used to share lecture notes and materials	2.42	0.88	LE
24.	SN is used for all the uploading of publications, articles and papers by lecturers	3.17	0.77	HE
25.	SN is used all for advertisement in the university	3.42	0.68	HE
26.	SN is used to share information and communicate between staff and students in schools	3.58	0.55	HE
Cluster Mean		3.06	0.80	HE

Table 3 showed that items 22 and 24 – 26 had high means scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. Item 22 had a mean score of 2.70 and a standard deviation of 1.11. This means that respondents agreed that social networking sites are for all notices for meetings and other functional purposes in universities management in Rivers State. Item 24 had a mean score of 3.17 and a standard deviation of 0.70. This means that respondents agreed that to a high extent

social networking sites are used for the uploading of publications, articles and papers by lecturers. Item 25 had a mean score of 3.42 and a standard deviation of 0.68. This means that to a high extent university management uses social network sites for most advertisements. Item 26 had a mean score of 3.58 and a standard deviation of 0.55. This means that to a very high extent university management uses social network sites to share most information and also used to communicate between staff and students in schools. Item 23 had low mean scores below the benchmark of 2.50. Item 23 had a mean score of 2.42 and a standard deviation of 0.88. This means that university management does not use many a time social networking sites to pass across lecture notes and materials. The cluster means score and standard deviation were 3.06 and 0.80 respectively. This showed that social network is used by university management to a high extent in River State.

Results of Hypotheses

The results of the hypotheses formulated and testable at 0.05 level of significance are presented as follows.

Results of Hypothesis 1 (Ho₁)

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female university administrators on the social network sites used in managing universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female university administrators on the social network sites used in managing universities in Rivers State.

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	3.342568	2.876747
Known Variance	0.6547	0.6398
Observations	625	625
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Z	16.98765	
P(Z<=z) one-tail	0.0000	
z Critical one-tail	1.674653	
P(Z<=z) two-tail	0.0000	
z Critical two-tail	1.786475	

Table 4 showed that z-value 16.9877 is significant at $P(Z \leq z)$ one-tail = 0.000 and $P(Z \leq z)$ two-tail = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This indicates there is a significant difference between the male and female administrators on the social network sites used in university management in Rivers State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean responses of female and male university administrators on the social network sites used in university management in Rivers State is rejected.

Results of Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female university administrators in areas social networks are used in university management in Rivers State.

Table 5: Z-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female university administrators in areas social network used in university management on the social network sites used in managing universities in Rivers State.

	Variable 1	Variable 2
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Mean	2.575269	1.33871
Known Variance	0.9432	0.9658
Observations	625	625
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Z	17.26169	
P(Z<=z) one-tail	0.0000	
z Critical one-tail	1.644854	
P(Z<=z) two-tail	0.0000	
z Critical two-tail	1.959964	

Table 5, the result shown z-value 17.2616 is significant at $P(Z \leq z)$ one-tail = 0.00 and $P(Z \leq z)$ two-tail = 0.00 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This indicates there is a significant difference between the male and female administrators in areas of social networks used in university management. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean responses of female and male university administrators in the areas social networks are used in university management in Rivers State is rejected.

Results of Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in opinion of male and female administrators on the extent social network are used in managing universities in Rivers state.

Table 5: Z-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female administrators on the extent social network are used in managing universities in Rivers state.

	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	3.416667	1.33871
Known Variance	0.9432	0.9658
Observations	625	625
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Z	29.00715	
P(Z<=z) one-tail	0.0000	
z Critical one-tail	1.644854	
P(Z<=z) two-tail	0.0000	
z Critical two-tail	1.959964	

From Table 5, the result showed that the z-value 29.00715 is significant at $p = 0.000$ which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$. This indicates there is a significant difference in the opinion of male and female administrators on the extent to which social networks are used in university management in Rivers State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in opinion of male and female administrators on the extent social network are used in university management in Rivers State is rejected.

IV. Discussion of Findings

The findings are discussed in the following order:

Discussion of research questions.

- Social network sites used in university management in Rivers State
- Areas Social network used in university management in Rivers State
- Extent social networking sites are used for university management in Rivers State

Discussion on the hypotheses

Social network sites used in managing universities in Rivers State

The findings in this regard showed that social networking sites are used in managing universities in Rivers State in this technological era. It showed that social network sites like Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp and LinkedIn are used in university management for communication. These findings agree with that of Akujua (2016) who found out that the social network sites that enhance the performance of students in secondary schools are: Facebook, WhatsApp, @go, and Twitter. In agreement with the findings of this study are the finding of Paul (2019) who found out that the various forms of western media programs used by secondary school students are: Twitter, Facebook, Eskimi, WhatsApp, Skype, Wechat, Q zone, Instagram, Imo, Viber, Line LinkedIn Telegram, Tumblr, googlet, Sina Weibo, Baidu Tieba, Pinterest, and Vkontakte (VK). Also, in consonance with the findings of this study are the assertion of Asemah & Edegoh, (2012) who stated that Social networking sites used in university management for communication are: Yahoo Messenger, Facebook Messenger, Blackberry Messenger (BBM), Google Talk, Google+ Messenger, iPhone, Androids and so on. These networking sites are used by most university personnel to interact in course of carrying out daily school activities. According to the authors, the expansion in technology also affected internet software leading to chatting sites known by the name "social media". With social networking sites, one can send and receive messages almost immediately.

Besides, Billington and Billington (2012) stated that based on the pervasive use and prevailing impact social media have on society, school administrators need to integrate these technologies and seek the best way to use social networks to the advantage in instructional delivery and communication among school personnel. The reason is that social networking has viral growth, connectivity, and ease of use, anonymity, global reach community, relevance, and a "smart" trend. The viral growth of usage requires everyone who wants to compete in the world of works globally to understand and utilize social network technologies. To that extent, they asserted that the school is the best environment to integrate social media into learning known as blended learning since most people in the society are associated with the latest technology.

Areas Social networks are used in managing universities in Rivers State

The findings in this regard showed that University management uses Social Network to discharge academic and administrative duties, Social Network (SN) are used for notification of events, Social Network are used for administrative purposes, University management uses Social Network (SN) for teaching and learning, University management uses Social Network (SN) for communication tool in schools, University management uses Social Network (SN) for recruitments, University management uses Social Network (SN) for online degree programmes and lectures, University management uses Social Network (SN) for meetings like zoom, Social Network is used for mass coverage of advertisement of universities events, Social Network is used to make public relation work easier, SNS is used to make access to information, materials and documents sharing easier, , SNS is used to make media documents sharable in short time, and Social Network is used for gratification and create relationship between staff of universities. These findings agree with that of Confetto& Siano (2018) stated that Social networks offer a variety of avenues through which we can communicate with people. Social media is known to have been used widely in the educational field also. Over the last 30 years, the nature of communication has undergone a substantial change and it is still changing. An email has had a profound effect on the way people keep in touch. Communications are shorter and more frequent than when letters were the norm and response time has greatly diminished. Instant messaging has created another method of interaction, one where the length of messages is

shorter and the style of the interaction is more conversational. Broadcast technologies like Twitter transform these short bursts of communication from one-on-one conversations to little news (or trivia) programs: which we can tune in whenever we want an update or have something to say.

Besides, online communication tools also have the potential to increase our awareness of the movements of our professional or social contacts. Twitter, for instance, offers us an update of things people we know happen to be doing at a particular point in time. This phenomenon has been referred to as social proprioception by Eberle (2011), named after the physical quality of proprioception that tells a creature where its extremities are by the reception of stimuli produced within the organism. Social proprioception tells us where the nodes of our community are and provides a sense of connectedness to and awareness of others without direct communication. Internet is the third place where people connect with friends, build a sense of togetherness. According to Nguyen & Fussell (2016), when it comes to social media and education. Some parents and teachers view these platforms as distractions that negatively influence students. But in today's increasingly digital world, social media plays a meaningful role in higher education every day. When used the right way, social media can enhance a student's learning journey, also making it much easier for pupils and educators to connect. Research has shown how beneficial social media can be in terms of learning. Through these various platforms, teachers can connect with students and incorporate social media into their lessons, making them more interesting, relatable and engaging. Social sites are a great tool when it comes to interacting with students since it's something they are so familiar with, using these sites frequently throughout daily life. The social network according to has promoted scholarship in higher education. Higher education and research go hand-in-hand. Social media has provided a base for universities and colleges to share their future-forward innovations and research opportunities with a much wider base than ever before Sehl (2020).

The extent of use of social networking sites for university management

Social network is used in university management systems. The social networking sites used is Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp and LinkedIn. In the works of Sweeny (2010), findings showed that managements of organizations which include universities adopted and used social media and social networking sites as a result of passive or active, proactive or reactive, and tactical or strategic uses. According to Moriconi (2014), the main factors that influence the adoption of SNSs in universities are the perceived usefulness, ease to use, social influence, facilitating conditions and social identity and the purpose of interaction. Social networking sites are mainly used for communication, meeting schedule notices and enhancement of advertisement by universities management to a very large extent. This is in line with the study of Kim, Newthm & Christen (2013) which disclosed that higher education institutions are using social media to engage with an audience well versed in new media channels. Social media is seen as a viable tool for university communicators due to its low cost, immediacy, and use by a large number of students.

Discussion of findings on hypotheses

The three null hypotheses were rejected. This indicated that there is a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female university administrators on social network sites used, areas social networks are used ant the extent social network sites are used in university management in Rivers state. This implies that gender plays a major role in how choices are made to a large extent among male and female administrators in using social network sites in university management in Rivers State. This is agreed by Confetto & Siano

(2018) who suggest that men are likely to have more time for the use of social networks because of gender expectations and roles. In other words, the societal expectations and norms tend to favour men over women who are expected to take care of the private sphere while men take care of the public sphere which the social network incorporates.

On the other hand, Zeevi (2013) averred that societal expectations tend to favour men. However, they argued that there are more women in the use of social media than men. In other words, Zeevi (2013) suggest that women outnumbered men for most social networking sites except LinkedIn. A 2009 Pew Internet Research report showed that women outnumbered men on social media platforms (Kim, Newth & Christen 2013). Another related study averred that females used Social Networking Sites predominantly to look for old friends and keep in touch with the existing ones while, at the same time, hiding their identities and personal information for privacy purposes (Nwabueze & Obaro, 2011). Another study that agreed with this difference of mean was that of (Tapscott, 2011), who found that men are more driven by contributory factors such as perceived usefulness, women are more motivated by process and social factors.

V. Conclusion

It is concluded from the study that

1. The social networking sites in management of universities in Rivers State include Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp.
2. The areas of social networking sites used in the management of universities in Rivers State include notification of events, invitation of staff for meetings, teaching and learning, communication for recruitment, online degree programmes, recording meeting proceedings, and resolving conflicts.
3. The extent to which social networks are used in the management of universities in Rivers State is high.
4. There is a significant difference in the mean response of male and female administrators on the social network sites used in the management of universities in Rivers state.
5. There is a significant difference in the mean response of male and female administrators on the areas social network sites are used in the management of universities in Rivers state.
6. There is a significant difference in the mean response of male and female administrators on the extent social network sites are used in managing universities in Rivers state

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made from the findings of the study

1. University should make it a policy to incorporate other social network sites such as LinkedIn, Myspace, QQ, QZone, YouTube, and Zoom
2. The gender gap should be bridged by organising orientation, conferences, workshops, or seminars on the use of social network sites by the administrative staff of universities in Rivers State.

References

- Akindutire, I. O. (2004). *Administration of higher education*. Sunray Press.
- Akujua, B.O. (2016). The influence of social network sites (Facebook) in the performance of secondary school students in Port-Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. *Unpublished NCE project of the National Teachers Institute, Kaduna.*
- Asemah, E.S. & Edegoh, L.O.N. (2012). Social media and insecurity in Nigeria: a critical

- appraisal. Being a paper presented at the 15th National Conference of African Council for Communication Education, which took place at the conference hall of the Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria, 15th – 19th March 2012.
- Asif, Z. & Khan, M. (2012). Users' perceptions of facebook's privacy policies. *ARPN Journal of Systems and Software*. 2(3), 119-121. Retrieved from <http://www.scientific-journals.org>
- Boyd, D.M. & Ellison, N.B. (2007). Social network sites: Definitions, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*. 3(4), 23-34.
- Confetto, M.G. & Siano, A. (2018). Social media content: A Management Framework. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 13(6), 84-96.
- Coyle, C. L. & Vaughtner, H. (2008). Social networking: Communication revolution or evolution. San Francisco: John Wiley & sons press.
- Gross, L.S. (2010). *Electronic media: An introduction* (3rd ed.), McGraw Hill International.
- Ibukun, W. O. (1997). *Educational management: Theory and practice*. Green-line publishers.
- Jukić, T. & Merlak, M. (2017). The use of social networking sites in public administration: The case of Slovenia. *The Electronic Journal of e-Government*. 15(1):2-18. Available online at www.ejeg.com
- Kim, M., Newth, D., & Christen, P. (2013). Modelling dynamics of diffusion across heterogeneous social networks: *News diffusion in social media entropy*. 15(10), 4215–4242. Retrieved on 2nd February 2019 from doi:10.3390/e15104215.
- Ladika, S. (2010). Socially evolved workforce management, 5th September 2010, pp 19-22.
- Lin, G. & Subrahmanyam, K. (2007). Adolescents and the net: Internet use and wellbeing. *Adolescence*. 42(168):659-675.
- Mathew, P.M. (2015). Influence of social media on the academic performance of higher secondary students. *Paripex – Indian Journal of Research*, 4(3), 6-7.
- Mgbekem, S. J. A. (2004). *Management of university education in Nigeria*. Unical Press.
- Moriconi, R. (2014). Collaboration between Brazilian and US institutions: The Time is ripe. In L.E. Rumbley, R.M. Helms, P.M. Peterson, & P.G. Altbach (Eds.) *Global opportunities and challenges for higher education leaders: Briefs on key themes*. Sense Publishers. 219-224.
- Nguyen, D. T., & Fussell, S. R. (2016). Effects of conversational involvement cues on understanding and emotions in instant messaging conversations. *Journal of Language & Social Psychology*, 35(1), 28-55. Retrieved on 5th May 2019 from DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0261927X15571538>
- Nwabueze, A.I. & Obaro, R.C. (2011). Social networking and instructional enhancements in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria: A New Educational Tool for Quality Improvement. *African Journal of Educational Research and Development (AJERD)*. 4(2b), 72-84.
- Odukunle, K.S. (2001). Funding of university education under democratic rule in Nigeria: problems and prospects. *Proceedings of the 12th general assembly of SSAN.4th -7th June 2001*.

- Paul, A.A. (2019). Effect of media access and cultural globalization among secondary school project of the National Teachers Institute, Kenneth Press.
- Raacke, J. & Bond-Raacke, J. (2008). MySpace and Facebook: Applying the uses and gratification theory to exploring friend-networking sites. *CyberPsychology & Behaviour*, 11(2):169-174.
- Sehl, K. (2020). *Social media in higher education: 8 essential tips*. Retrieved from <https://blog.hootsuite.com/social-media-in-higher-education> on 22nd November 2020.
- Seth, S.C. (2019). The important role of social media in higher education. Retrieved on 22nd November 2020 from <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/handle/10125/59696...>
Unpublished NCE in Port-Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- Sweeny, S. M. (2010). Writing for the instant messaging and text messaging generation: Using new literacies to support writing instruction. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 54(2), 121-130 Retrieved on 10th May 2019 from DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1598/JAAL.54.2.4>
- Tapscott, D. (2011). View of the age of networked intelligence: Unleashing the power of social networking for the enterprise. Moxie Software. Retrieved on 5th May. 2019 from http://www.e2conf.com/innovate/exhibitor-whitepapers/Don_Tapscott--Social_Networking_for_the_Enterprise.pdf.
- Waddell, D., Jones, G.R. & George, J.M. (2011). *Contemporary management*. 2nd (eds.), McGraw-Hill.
- Zeevi, D. (2013). The ultimate history of Facebook [INFOGRAPHIC]. *Social Media Today.Socialmediatoday.com*. Retrieved 29th December 2019, from <http://socialmediatoday.com/daniel-zeevi/1251026/ultimate-history-facebook-infographic>.